

USE OF FLIPPED INSTRUCTION IN LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS; AN INVESTIGATION ABOUT STUDENT TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract:

Flipped instruction reinforces the idea that learning cannot be limited to classrooms. Flipped instruction is a new way of teaching for language pedagogy as other fields. Thus, the present research aimed to find out student teachers' perspectives about flipped instruction and flipped instruction based syllabus which was designed specifically for speaking skills development. The current study was utilized qualitative method to collect the data. Structured written interview technique and student teachers' response papers were used to collect student teachers' perspectives about flipped instruction and flipped instruction based Oral Communication Skills I course. The participants were Pre-service English Language Teaching Department student teachers who were first graders of ELT department at Gazi University, Turkey. Participants consisted of 23 students who were 20 female and 3 male student teachers. Results showed that student teachers had positive attitudes towards flipped instruction, which was quite new for the student teachers. The results indicated that student teachers were satisfied with flipped instruction and flipped syllabus which was specifically designed for the course. Besides, student teachers thought that flipped instruction was effective to make them prepared for the lesson and speaking activities which are carried out in class times.

Keywords: flipped instruction, speaking skills, English language teaching, blended learning, student teachers

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1. Introduction

Today, knowing a language refers to being able to speak in that language (Ur, 1996), and thus, speaking seems much more important than the other skills such as listening, reading and writing skills in second language learning (Egan, 1999; Ur, 1996). As one of the important component of language, speaking skill has a great role in use of language. In general, speaking skills may be defined as *“the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts”* (Chaney and Burke, 1998, p.13). Despite, speaking skill's major importance, it has been neglected in schools and universities (Egan, 1999). Besides, teaching speaking still remains a challenge for many teachers (Burns, 2012). In related literature, it is possible to see various reasons for ignoring and neglecting speaking skills in foreign language classrooms. According to Ur (1996), speaking skill is neglected due to teachers' focusing on other skills, difficulty of designing and administering speaking activities. Shumin (2002) states difficulty of speaking a language is the reason for the ignoring speaking skills.

According to Dörnyei (2005) anxiety and motivational factors are the reasons for ignoring. Yılmaz Yakışık (2012) mentions lack of testing and evaluation of speaking can be counted among reasons. Considering Turkey as an EFL context, teaching speaking skill is often neglected by language teachers. According to Ozsevik (2010) English language teachers own speaking deficiency is one of the reasons for neglecting speaking skill. Besides, Özkan (2013) mentions limited teaching hours within academic year and limitation of time that is devoted to preparing speaking tasks and its administration in language classrooms. In addition, Kırkgöz (2008) mentions teachers' transmission-based educational culture and large classrooms are the reasons for the lack of communicative activities in foreign language classrooms. As there are various reasons of neglecting teaching speaking skills an alternative way of instruction may enhance teaching speaking skills in language classrooms. Flipped Instruction is overemphasized in recent years as Blended Learning, Distance Education, Computer Assisted Language Learning. Flipped classroom is a part of blended learning in which students have control over *“time, place, path and/or pace”* during their learning (Staker and Horn, 2012). Besides, they are active participants of the process (Arfstrom, Hamdan, Mcknight and Mcknight, 2013). However, flipped learning is different than Distance Learning or E-learning. While students learn contents completely online in Distance Learning and E-learning, students deliver the learning materials or video lectures through online delivery and they spend classroom hours to feedback and collaborative learning with teacher and peers in flipped learning. Flipping the classroom reinforces the idea that learning is not

restricted with “*brick-and-mortar location*” establishments (Staker and Horn, 2012). Simple but clear definition is made by Lage, Platt, and Treglia (2000, p.32) “*Inverting the classroom means that events that have traditionally taken place inside the classroom now take place outside the classroom and vice versa*”.

Sams (2011) is one of founders of flipped classroom and he asserts that there is not a one way to flip the classroom. One can flip the classroom partly or as a whole. The main idea of flipping the classroom is that all active learning should be done in classroom hours and all passive learning can be done at home or wherever students want. As it is understood from the main idea, flipped learning has its roots from social constructivism. As Bergman and Sams (2012) state, active learning has a key role in flipped classroom. Teacher and peers are in collaboration during active learning process. As Lambert (2013) says, flipped learning is a stage in the evolution of blended learning and flipped learning is evolving continuously due to educators and students' needs (Sams, 2011). Flipped classroom model provides flexibility to both teacher and students that they tailor the curriculum and spend class time on production (Bergman and Sams, 2012). As flipped classroom model provides positive opportunities it has been used in various fields. When it is examined in related literature, it can be seen that flipped classroom approach has been used in various contexts successfully such as science (Bergman and Sams, 2012), math (Fulton, 2013; Johnson, 2007), in Language Arts (Fulton, 2013; Ullman, 2013) and in higher education contexts with pharmaceutical students (Ryan, 2013), statistics courses (Strayer, 2007), and cinema and TV arts students (Enfield, 2013).

As a recent instruction model, flipped instruction provides new and innovative ways of learning experience to learners. Flipping the classrooms allow students to have more interactional classroom environments. On the contrary, to traditional lecture based model flipped instruction reverses the content and homework. Thus, class times are spent with more interactional and productive activities. As a productive skill, speaking skills are fostered through practice and the nature of flipped instruction provides more practice and production opportunities to language learners. In this respect the current research is significant to provide an alternative way. When, Turkey's situation is considered as an EFL context, flipped instruction may provide more opportunity to develop language learners' speaking skills. This research aims to find out pre-service English language teachers' attitudes towards flipped instruction and flipped instruction based syllabus for Oral Communication Skills I course. The current research is guided by one research question which is presented below;

2. Research Question

What are the student teachers' perceptions towards flipped instruction and flipped instruction based Oral Communication Skills I course in the experimental group?

3. Material and Methods

The current study is utilized qualitative method to collect the data. The data were collected at the beginning of the 2014 - 2015 fall term. Structured written interview technique is used to collect student teachers' perspectives about flipped instruction and flipped instruction based Oral Communication Skills I course. Considering the Turkey as an EFL context, language learners do not have frequent opportunity to improve their speaking skills in English. As the classroom hours generally are spent to teach structure of English and other skills such as reading and writing, speaking skills are neglected in language classrooms. The related research shows that language learners are not fully capable of speaking in target language (Demirel, 2004; Paker, 2012). The participants are Pre-service English Language Teaching Department student teachers who are first graders of ELT department at Gazi University. Participants consist of 23 students who are 20 female and 3 male student teachers.

4. Results and Discussion

Qualitative data include student teachers' interview. The researcher creates 21 positive and negative themes to categorize and analyze qualitative data due to latent content analysis. The themes consist of 17 positive and 4 negative themes. These themes are created due to student teachers' responses to interview questions. Qualitative data include 23 written structured interviews which have 7 open-ended questions. These themes and their codes are presented below;

Table 1: Positive and Negative Themes for Qualitative Data Analysis

Positive & Negative Themes	Code
1 Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities	PLS
2 Pre-knowledge about the topic	PKT
3 More willing to speak & participation	WSP
4 Useful website & way to get materials	WM
5 Internet connection problems	IC
6 Problem with materials	PM
7 Self-confidence & courage in Speaking	SCS
8 Productive speaking activities	PSA
9 Positive classroom atmosphere	PCA
10 Spontaneous speaking development	SSD
11 Related materials& lesson	RML
12 Positive views about relation	PIR
13 Positive impact on language domains	PILD
14 Positive impact on Grammar	PIG
15 Positive impact on Vocabulary	PIC
16 Positive impact on Pronunciation	PIP
17 Negative ideas about Grammar development	NGD
18 More time for practice	MTP
19 Negative views about assignments	NVA
20 Positive views about assignments	PVA
21 Positive views about the course	PVC

An overall qualitative data analysis is presented below and the detailed analysis is provided one by one.

Figure 1: Frequency of themes

As the figure 1 presents student teachers in experimental group think that flipped instruction is effective to make them prepared for the lesson and speaking activities

which are carried in class times. Besides, they think that studying learning materials before the lesson provide pre-knowledge about the topic and they become more willing to speak in speaking activities. Another significant result is that students are satisfied with having time to spend productive speaking activities. Thus, they do not have to cover learning materials in class times. As the last significant result, all the student teachers have positive attitudes towards flipped instruction and flipped instruction based Oral Communication Skills I course.

4.1 Results and Responses for Q1

Student teacher interview includes seven questions to collect experimental group student teachers' ideas about Oral Communication Skills I course which has been taught through flipped instruction to student teachers. The first question aims to find out participants' positive or negative thoughts about having materials before the lesson through Edmodo and its effects on their preparation for the lesson.

Q1: 'What do you think about having materials before the lesson through Edmodo? What are the positive or negative effects on your preparation for the lesson? Please give some details'.

According to participants' responses to question one, four positive and two negative themes has been created. Frequency of responses has been presented on a table below. These themes are coded and presented below;

Positive Themes;

1. Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities (Coded as PLS)
2. Pre-knowledge about the topic (Coded as PKT)
3. More willing to speak & participation (Coded as WSP)
4. Useful website & way to get materials (Coded as WM)

Negative Themes;

1. Internet connection problems (Coded as IC)
2. Problem with materials (Coded as PM)

Figure 2: Frequency of themes in Q1 responses

As it is seen in the graph, the highest frequency belongs to 'Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities' coded as 'PLS'. Most of the participants think that getting materials before the lesson through Edmodo makes student teachers prepared for the lesson and speaking activities which are carried out in classroom hours. 'Pre-knowledge about the topic' coded as 'PKT' and 'more willing to speak & participation' coded as 'WSP' have same frequency rate with 13 repetitions in participants' responses to Q1. Participants think that they join to the lesson well-prepared with the help of getting materials beforehand and they speak more easily in speaking activities. Thus, they have background knowledge about the topic.

Besides, participants think that Edmodo is a useful website to share materials, their ideas with other students and to get materials. Participants' responses to Q1 lead researcher to create two negative themes for Q1. These themes are; 'Internet connection problems' coded as 'IC' and 'Problem with materials' coded as 'PM'. The responses show that student teachers sometimes have some internet connection difficulty to get materials from Edmodo in their dormitory. Besides a few student teachers complains about the length of reading passages. The frequencies of negative themes are quite few as it is seen in the table. Some of the responses related with appropriate theme are provided below;

R1: 'By getting materials beforehand through Edmodo enables me to be wide-awake during the lesson time (More willing to speak & participation WSP) because I know about the topic so I have an opinion about the subject (Pre-knowledge about the

topic PKT). That pushes me to speak more and in that way my speaking skills sharpens'.

R2: 'I think having materials before lesson has many opportunities. For example, we come to lesson well-prepared (Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities PLS) and being aware of the topic (Pre-knowledge about the topic PKT). Therefore, class activity is getting better (More willing to speak & participation WSP) and nearly all students have an idea on subject (Pre-knowledge about the topic PKT). Negative side of it, some students focus on only materials, they don't make investigation about topic.

R3: 'Having materials before the lesson is really important for me because I have some ideas before the class Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities PLS) when I read a text about the topic. We can't talk fluently without preparation more willing to speak & participation WSP). For this reason, there are more positive effects than negative ones. But sometimes when the texts are too long, we have difficulty about reading effectively Problem with materials PM).

4.2 Results and Responses for Q2

Second question aims to find out participants' ideas about use of classroom hours effectiveness on their speaking skills development. The question is;

Q2: 'How do you spend your class time in Oral Communication Skills I course? What are the effects of classroom activities on your speaking skills? Please give some details'.

According to student teachers' responses to question two, four positive themes have been created. Frequency of responses has been presented on a table below. These themes are coded and presented below;

Positive Themes for Q2;

1. Self-confidence & courage in Speaking (Coded as SCS)
2. Productive speaking activities (Coded as PSA)
3. Positive classroom atmosphere (Coded as PCA)
4. Spontaneous speaking development (Coded as SSD)

Figure 3: Frequency of themes in Q2 responses

As it is presented in graph, responses which are given by students to question 2 emerge four positive themes. These themes include 'Self-confidence & courage in Speaking, SCS', 'Productive speaking activities, PSA', 'Positive classroom atmosphere, PCA' and 'Spontaneous speaking development, SSD'. It is seen that most of the student teachers think that class times have been spent with productive speaking activities which improve students' speaking skills. Thus, 'Productive speaking activities, PSA' has been repeated twenty times in students' responses for Q2. In addition, participants think that Oral Communication Skills I course which has been taught through flipped Instruction made them gain self-confidence and courage in speaking English. One another result is that student teachers have a positive way of thinking about classroom atmosphere and they think that this atmosphere helps them to speak English more effectively and freely. As the graph presented above, student teachers also think that the course enhance their spontaneous speaking skills. Some of the participants' responses are presented below with their themes;

R1: 'In class time, at first, we have a conversation about topic. We speak about what we understand from text and videos. Then we do some different activities such as dramas, games (Productive speaking activities, PSA). Thanks to these activities, I gain self-confidence more, and I gain more opportunities about speaking (Self-confidence & courage in Speaking, SCS) and (Spontaneous speaking development, SSD).

R2: 'Sometimes, we have role-plays (Productive speaking activities, PSA), so we have an opportunity to think quickly and this opportunity helps us to communicate well when we have to speak foreign people (Spontaneous speaking development, SSD)'.
'

R3: 'I am trying to speak about topics. You are so tolerated about our mistakes and it makes me feel comfortable while speaking (Positive classroom atmosphere, PCA) and (Self-confidence & courage in Speaking, SCS). Sometimes, we make different activities like drama, interview, making up a story (Productive speaking activities, PSA). They are so essential to speak spontaneously (Spontaneous speaking development, SSD)'.

4.3 Results and Responses for Q3

Question three aims to reveal the relation between the materials which have been posted to Edmodo before the lesson and productive classroom activities. Besides, Q3 asks about the kinds of materials.

Q3: 'What kind of materials do you have before the lessons in Edmodo? Please exemplify the relation between materials you had before the lessons in Edmodo and classroom activities'

Student teachers' responses indicate that four positive theme can be created for Q3. These themes are 'Prepared for the lesson& speaking, coded as PLS', 'Pre-knowledge about the topic, coded as PKT', 'Related materials& lesson, coded as RML' and 'Positive views about relation coded as PIR2.

'Prepared for the lesson& speaking, coded as PLS' and 'Pre-knowledge about the topic, coded as PKT' are the same themes with Q1. The third and fourth themes have been created for Q3.

Positive Themes for Q3;

1. Prepared for the lesson& speaking (coded as PLS)
2. Pre-knowledge about the topic (coded as PKT)
3. Related materials& lesson (coded as RML)
4. Positive views about relation (coded as PIR)

Figure 4: Frequency of themes in Q3 responses

As the figure shows above most of the student teachers have the idea that materials which are posted through Edmodo before the lessons are related with class times. The responses for 'Related materials & lesson, RML' have the highest rate among themes. Besides, student teachers have a positive attitude towards having materials beforehand. Thus, 'Positive ideas about relation, PIR' has the second highest rate. Another significant result of Q3 response is, most of the student teachers think that materials on Edmodo are useful to get prepared for the lessons and productive activities in classroom. In addition, they think materials provide pre-knowledge about the topic which is the theme of the week. Some student's responses are provided below;

R1: 'We have some texts and videos in Edmodo. These materials help us during classroom activities (Positive ideas about relation, PIR), (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS), (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT). While we are speaking we use the information that we learn from Edmodo (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS). When we are doing classroom activities, I try to remember the materials and I can create ideas through these materials (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS) and (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT)'.

R2: 'In general, materials include videos related to topic, texts, and articles and so on. The videos are always specific to the topic and even the hardest topic to grasp turns into a piece of cake through the videos (Positive ideas about relation, PIR), (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS), (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT) (Related materials& lesson, RML). Besides reading text and trying to comprehend, we watch videos related to topic and up to now, all subjects we learned make sense. That is an amazing thing (Positive ideas about relation, PIR)'.

R3: 'Knowing what we study in the lesson makes us more effective (Positive ideas about relation, PIR), (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS) and give us more example and idea about the lesson (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS), (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT) (Related materials& lesson, RML)'.

4.4 Results and Responses for Q4

Question four aims to find out participants' point of views about the effects of getting materials on their speaking skills especially for fluency and accuracy. The question is;

Q4: 'How does getting materials on Edmodo before lessons affect your speaking skills development? Do you think getting materials before the lessons improved your fluency and accuracy?'

Question four responses are analyzed under three themes of which two themes are the same theme with Q2. These are; 'Prepared for the lesson& speaking, coded as PLS' and 'Pre-knowledge about the topic, coded as PKT'. The third theme is created for Q4, which is 'Positive impact on language domains, coded as PILD'. The themes for Q4 are;

Positive Themes for Q4;

1. Prepared for the lesson& speaking (coded as PLS)
2. Pre-knowledge about the topic (coded as PKT)
3. Positive impact on language domains (coded as PILD)

Figure 5: Frequency of themes in Q4 responses

The results of Q4 responses show that student teachers are aware of the fact that materials make them prepared for the lesson and provide pre-knowledge for classroom activities. As classroom activities require participation of student teachers, they have necessary information before the class times. Some of the participant state that having

information before lessons make them feel more comfortable and relaxed during speaking activities. As the results presented on the figure above, student teachers commented that materials prepare them for the lessons and productive activities. Nearly, all of the student teachers are agree on getting materials before the lessons improved their fluency and accuracy in speaking. Besides, student teachers think that materials improve their pronunciation and vocabulary knowledge too. Some participants' responses are presented below with appropriate theme;

R1: 'Yes, it improves our fluency because we have ideas and thoughts in order when we are prepared beforehand (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS), (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT). However, it doesn't mean we don't speak spontaneously, which we do in classroom activities. I think, speaking spontaneously during the lessons balances this situation (Positive impact on language domains, PILD)'.

R2: 'Definitely, it contributes my speaking skills a lot. Think that while we speak to a friend, we think about what we say next; how we respond to him/her. Just like that getting materials before lesson enable us to gain time to think over the subject and to define what my perspective over the topic is before (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS), (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT). In this way, I gain control over my words, my fluency and accuracy (Positive impact on language domains, PILD). By the way watching the topic-related videos makes me aware of the correct pronunciations and collocations of the vocabularies (Positive impact on language domains, PILD)'.

R3: 'I totally agree with the statement because getting materials previously make us be aware of the topic (Pre-knowledge about the topic, PKT) and think clearly before speak. When you know the subject and you think about what you are going to talk improve your fluency and accuracy, because you are prepared (Prepared for the lesson& speaking, PLS)'.

4.5 Results and Responses for Q5

Similar to Q4, question five aims to figure out the effects of getting materials on Edmodo before the lessons on participants' grammar use, vocabulary choice and pronunciation. Question five is;

Q5: 'How does getting materials on Edmodo before lessons affect your grammar use, vocabulary choice and pronunciation? Give some details'.

Q5 includes three language domains which are grammar use, vocabulary choice and pronunciation. Thus, four new themes are created for Q5, three of them are positive themes and one of them is negative theme. These themes are as follows;

Positive themes for Q5;

1. Positive impact on Grammar (Coded as PIG)
2. Positive impact on Vocabulary (Coded as PIC)
3. Positive impact on Pronunciation (Coded as PIP)
Negative themes for Q5;
 1. Negative ideas about Grammar development (Coded as NGD)

Figure 6: Frequency of themes in Q5 responses

As the graph presents, most of the student teachers think that materials which are uploaded on Edmodo before the lesson, improved their vocabulary knowledge. Thus, the theme 'Positive impact on Vocabulary, PIC' has the highest rate of frequency among positive themes for Q5. Besides, student teachers have the idea that materials especially the videos on Edmodo helps them to learn correct pronunciation of new vocabularies and correct spelling of known words by students. The theme 'Positive impact on Pronunciation, PIP' has the second highest frequency rate with 13. There is a contrary point of view about materials impact on Grammar use. Some of the student teachers think that materials have a positive impact on Grammar use development. Thus, the theme 'Positive impact on Grammar, PIG' has 9 repetitions in students' responses for Q5. On the other hand, the negative theme for Q5 'Negative ideas about Grammar development, NGD' has 6 repetitions. The results show that most of the students have positive ideas about getting materials before the lesson has a positive impact on vocabulary and pronunciation development. Student teachers state that they have chance for searching unknown words, phrases and collocations before the lesson when they have the materials of the week. Moreover, getting materials before the lesson make students responsible for their own learning for the lesson. Another important result is

student teachers reuse the materials during class times. Some student teachers' responses are presented below;

R1: 'First of all, I learn some vocabulary from the materials on Edmodo 'Positive impact on Vocabulary, PIC', and then after the day I use these words during the lessons and memorize them easily, which is the same for pronunciation 'Positive impact on Pronunciation, PIP'. Thus, I pay attention to my Grammar because I have draft on my mind 'Positive impact on Grammar, PIG'.

R2: 'When I get the materials, I read and highlight the unknown words and the Grammar structures sounding different 'Positive impact on Vocabulary, PIC' and 'Positive impact on Grammar, PIG' and then I searched for these on the Web. That results in an entire learning cycle surrounding pronunciation, collocation and Grammar 'Positive impact on Vocabulary, PIC', 'Positive impact on Grammar, PIG' and 'Positive impact on Pronunciation, PIP'.

R3: 'While I am watching the videos, I learn how to pronounce the words which I don't know 'Positive impact on Pronunciation, PIP'. On the other hand, I learn vocabularies and phrases thanks to the materials on Edmodo 'Positive impact on Vocabulary, PIC'.

4.6 Results and Responses for Q6

Question six aims to seek students' point of view about the use of classroom times when they get materials before the lessons. Q6 is;

Q6: 'What do you think about the time allotted for the classroom activities when you have materials before the lesson? Please share our ideas'.

In the light of participants' responses for Q6, responses are analyzed under three positive themes. The two themes are the same with Q1 themes. These themes are 'Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities, PLS' and 'more willing to speak & participation, WSP'. The third theme is created for Q6, which is 'More time for practice, MTP'.

Positive themes for Q6;

1. Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities (Coded as PLS)
2. More willing to speak & participation (Coded as WSP)
3. More time for practice (Coded as MTP)

Figure 7: Frequency of themes in Q6 responses

As it is presented on the figure above, all of the participants think that they have more time for productive classroom activities when they get materials on Edmodo before the lesson. The theme 'More time for practice, MTP' has the 30 repetition in students' responses for Q6. Another important result of Q6 responses is students think they are well-prepared to the lesson thanks to materials on Edmodo. Thus, the theme 'Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities, PLS' has 15 repetitions. As the last important result, student teachers are more willing to speak and participate in classroom activities when they know the topic and class times have been used for productive classroom activities. The theme 'More willing to speak & participation, WSP' has 8 repetitions in student's responses for Q6. Some of the participants' responses are presented below with appropriate themes;

R1: 'Since we know the subject and come to lesson well-prepared we can manage the time beneficially 'More time for practice, MTP' and 'Being prepared for the lesson & speaking activities, PLS'. For example, teacher will not have to explain the topic for each of us and that will not time consuming. We spend much time in the class with activities, speaking and sharing ideas 'More time for practice, MTP' and 'More willing to speak & participation, WSP'.

R2: 'Having materials before the lesson saves our class times 'More time for practice, MTP'. We get rid of reading texts, watching videos during the lesson so we can interact more with each other and we gain intimacy to one another 'More time for practice, MTP' and 'More willing to speak & participation, WSP'. Moreover, we perform dramas with the rest of time. It is joyful and really beloved for me 'More time for practice, MTP'.

R3: 'The time allotted for classroom activities is definitely enough. We had lots of classroom activities so far thanks to Edmodo 'More time for practice, MTP'. I like all of

them. That was important for us to speak up and act out spontaneously 'More willing to speak & participation, WSP'.

4.7 Results and Responses for Q7

Question seven aims to find out the impact of assignments on classroom activities which have been carried out in Oral Communication Skill I course. Q7 is as follow;

Q7: 'Tell me about the kind of assignments you have before the lessons. Do the assignments have a positive or negative effect on classroom activities in Oral Communication Skills I course?'

Responses for Q7 led the researcher to create two positive and one negative theme for Q7 response analysis. One of the positive theme is the same theme with Q1, which is 'Prepared for the lesson, coded as PLS'. Second positive theme is created for Q7, which is 'Positive views about assignments, coded as PVA'. Negative theme is 'Negative views about assignments, coded as NVA'. To be clear, these themes are provided below with their codes;

Positive themes for Q7;

1. Prepared for the lesson (Coded as PLS)
2. Positive views about assignments (Coded as PVA)

Negative theme for Q7;

1. Negative views about assignments (Coded as NVA)

Figure 8: Frequency of themes in Q7 responses

As the graph presents, all of the student teachers have the idea that the assignments are useful for classroom activities and they are effective to develop student teachers'

language skills such as writing, questioning skill, etc. The theme 'Positive views about assignments, PVA' has the 39 repetition in students' responses for Q7. The results show student teachers do not think that assignments are burden for them. On the contrary, they think that assignments are part of classroom activities and useful for their development. Another result of Q7 responses is that the theme 'Prepared for the lesson, PLS' has 10 repetitions in responses. So, student teachers think that assignments are useful tools to make them prepared for the lesson. Another result is the theme 'Negative views about assignments, NVA' has 6 repetitions in responses. Few of the student teachers have negative points of view about the assignments. Some participants' responses are provided below;

R1: 'While doing reading assignments I take some notes, key points about the subject thanks to that I can be more confident in classroom activities 'Prepared for the lesson, PLS' and 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'.

R2: 'When we have assignments before the lessons we can remember the things that we talk about. We write some questions before the lesson and we think about them 'Prepared for the lesson, PLS' and 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'. These things make this lesson enjoyable 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'. We have fun while sharing our ideas and questions 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'.

R3: 'Generally, we prepare questions about the passage and write a paragraph. Then we ask that question to our friends. This really improves our speaking skills 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'. When it comes to writing a paragraph, Although, the lesson is related to speaking skills we can develop our writing skills, so assignments are really important for me 'Positive views about assignments, PVA'.

5. Conclusion

Qualitative data were collected to find answers to research question of the study. The results of data are presented in findings section in details. As the findings show that student teachers have positive attitudes towards flipped instruction which is quite new for the student teachers. Although, they do not have any previous knowledge about instruction and its way of use, student teachers easily understood the procedures. According to student teachers' responses to individual interview, positive and negative themes were created. The themes include 17 positive and 4 negative themes. The results indicate that student teachers are satisfied with flipped instruction and flipped syllabus which is specifically designed for Oral Communication Skills I course. Besides, student teachers think that flipped instruction is effective to make them prepared for the lesson and speaking activities which are carried out in class times. In addition, they think that

studying learning materials before the lesson provides pre-knowledge about the topic and they become more willing to speak in speaking activities. Another significant result is that student teachers are satisfied with having time to spend productive speaking activities. The syllabus was designed as theme-based syllabus which includes pedagogical tasks to enrich class times within the purposes of making student teachers more competent English speakers. As, syllabus contain pedagogical tasks, student teachers have chance to spend class times effectively to develop their speaking skills. These pedagogical tasks cover various speaking activities in which each and every student teacher have chance to use language. Besides, these tasks were carried out through pair work, group work, games, drama and role-play formats. As it is mentioned in literature review section, student-centered learning theories emphasize the importance of active learning in which student teachers are active constructors of their own learning (Tétreault, 2006; Vygotsky, 1978). In addition, the syllabus was designed to develop student teachers' speaking skills in collaboration to other skills as reading, writing and listening. As findings reveal that nearly all of the student teacher in experimental group has positive perceptions towards flipped instruction. As the last conclusion, data of the study reveal that student teachers have positive attitudes towards flipped instruction which is quite new for them.

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